

DOI: 10.15276/ETR.01.2024.11
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10982674
UDC: 379.8
JEL: Z32

ANALYSIS OF THE NEED FOR REGIONAL HEALTH AND TREATMENT TOURIST DESTINATIONS FOR CHILDREN

АНАЛІЗ ПОТРЕБИ В РЕГІОНАЛЬНИХ ОЗДОРОВЧО-ЛІКУВАЛЬНИХ ТУРИСТИЧНИХ ДЕСТИНАЦІЯХ ДЛЯ ДІТЕЙ

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Received 12.02.2024

Добрянська Н.А., Черноусова С.С., Саленко Л.Р. Аналіз потреби в регіональних оздоровчо-лікувальних туристичних дестинаціях для дітей. Оглядова стаття.

Розглянуто важливість та перспективи розвитку лікувально-оздоровчого туризму з врахуванням нестабільної геополітичної ситуації, що склалася в країні після повномасштабного вторгнення РФ. Надано рекомендації для збалансованого розвитку лікувально-оздоровчих дестинацій. Проаналізовано за допомогою SWOT-аналізу стратегії розвитку оздоровчо-лікувальних туристичних дестинацій для дітей в Одеському регіоні. Досліджено шляхом анкетування попит на надання оздоровчо-лікувальних послуг для дітей. Проведене дослідження є важливою складовою сталого розвитку туристичної індустрії в Одеському регіоні, а також і для держави в цілому.

Ключові слова: туризм, дестинація, лікувально-оздоровчий туризм, стратегія розвитку лікувально-оздоровчого туризму для дітей, Одеський регіон

Dobrianska N.A., Chernousova S.S., Salenko L.R. Analysis of the Need for Regional Health and Treatment Tourist Destinations for Children. Review article.

The article considers the importance and prospects for the development of medical and health tourism, taking into account the unstable geopolitical situation in the country after the full-scale invasion of Russia. Recommendations for the balanced development of health and wellness destinations are provided. The article analyses the strategies for the development of health-improving tourist destinations for children in the Odesa region using the SWOT analysis. The demand for the provision of health and medical services for children is studied by means of a questionnaire. The study is an important component of the sustainable development of the tourism industry in the Odesa region, as well as for the state as a whole.

Keywords: tourism, destination, health tourism, strategy of development of health tourism for children, Odesa region

Medical tourism is constantly developing and gaining more and more importance in the modern world. This type of tourism is aimed at improving the health and general well-being of people with the help of medical and wellness procedures, as well as recreation in an appropriate environment. One of the key factors in the development of health tourism is the growing interest in a healthy lifestyle and the demand for services aimed at supporting physical and mental health. Researching the topic of development of regional health and medical tourism destinations for children is important, since this category of the population is vulnerable and their health requires special attention and care, and access to quality medical care and health procedures can positively affect their physical and psychological condition; on the other hand, such institutions can play a key role in the development of tourism in a specific region, since the creation and development of such places will contribute to attracting tourists, increasing the tourist flow and increasing the economic potential of the region.

Analysis of recent research and publications

The issue of terminology and development of medical and health tourism has been studied by many scholars, among whom are K. Halasiuk, S. Halasiuk, M. Rutynskyi, V. Petranivskyi, A. Parfinenko, I. Volkova, V. Shcherbyna, L. Melnyk, S. Batychenko, O. Dolynska, G. Brusiltseva. The scientists considered issues in the field of medical and health tourism, in particular at the regional level as a whole or in the context of different regions.

Unsolved aspects of the problem

During the military actions of the Russian Federation, healthcare facilities in Ukraine almost ceased to develop, as the state allocates funds exclusively for minimal expenses. One of the important problems that remains unresolved is the provision of recommendations for the balanced development of health and wellness destinations, as well as the lack of such a study for the Odesa region. After all, it has significant potential for the development of health tourism due to its location, climate and natural resources. The Odesa region is famous for its resorts and sanatoriums, which provide a variety of medical and health services. Many of them specialise in the treatment of respiratory, cardiovascular, musculoskeletal and neurological diseases. They often offer treatment with mineral waters, mud, physiotherapy and other methods that have a positive impact on health.

The aim of the article is to emphasise that the unstable geopolitical situation has a significant impact on the development of health tourism, and to present the study conducted on the possibilities and necessity of developing health tourism, and hence the institutions themselves, for children on the example of the Odesa region under martial law.

The main part

Ukraine has a variety of natural and recreational resources, on the basis of which sanatorium and resort facilities operate. However, the effectiveness of their work can currently be recognised as unsatisfactory due to a number of reasons that complicate competition in the industry. Therefore, there is an objective need to change management priorities and bring the industry to international standards, which is currently impossible without the involvement of public-private partnerships.

Ukraine's tourism industry is based on market mechanisms and is a significant source of revenue for local and state budgets. Tourism serves as a means of providing affordable and comprehensive recreation and health improvement for the population. The natural resource potential, combined with a favourable geographical location, creates sufficient preconditions for the development of this industry.

In many countries, tourism is the main source of income, which determines the dependence of their economic situation on international tourism. However, the tourism product is a non-staple commodity with elastic and unstable demand, which depends on various

statistical and dynamic factors. The presence of favourable factors leads to the leadership of certain regions and countries in global tourism, and, conversely, undesirable factors reduce the tourist flow. Over the past decade, the global economy has been developing much more slowly [1].

The relevance of geopolitical aspects has increased due to the decrease in the level of external military threat in Ukraine. Thus, the main topic for the UN World Tourism Organisation has become improving security and ensuring unhindered travel.

At the regional and national levels, demand for tourism services will remain extremely volatile, and in the 21st century this is increasingly linked to political factors. Among them, it is important to highlight internal political instability, terrorism and armed conflicts as the main factors affecting the tourism market. Political factors can cause significant fluctuations in tourist demand, as insecurity and uncertainty in politics can affect the safety and comfort of tourists. Domestic political instability, for example, can lead to protests, demonstrations, or even political change, creating uncertainty for tourists. Terrorist attacks and armed conflicts can pose serious threats to the safety of tourists, leading to travel deterrence and cancellations of travel plans. Political instability can also affect the image of a country and cause a decrease in tourist interest [2].

The impact of political instability on the tourism sector of a destination country is manifested in a decrease in the inflow of international visitors and a decrease in the profitability of the industry. However, geopolitical instability can lead to changes and reformatting of the tourism market, and for some countries this can be an opportunity for tourism development. Even with Ukraine's high tourism potential and positive dynamics, the country failed to become a leading tourist destination due to the loss of territories and hostilities, which led to a negative balance of tourist flows. A few setbacks and problems do not prevent the country from considering the examples of other countries, such as Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Serbia, Cyprus, Egypt, and Israel, which quickly restored their tourism market after large-scale conflicts [3].

The development of health and medical tourism may be affected by the unstable geopolitical situation, but new opportunities may also arise. Consider the possible prospects in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Prospects for the development of health and treatment tourism

Source: the authors' own elaboration

An unstable geopolitical situation may affect tourists' choice of destination. Tourists may seek safer or less risky regions for their travels, which may lead to changes in popular health and wellness destinations. In an unstable environment, tourists may be more interested in countries or regions where there is a high level of healthcare and security. Instability in certain regions may lead to an increase in demand for medical services abroad, and tourists may seek out countries with a high standard of medical care that offer health and wellness programmes.

The unstable geopolitical situation may accelerate the development of telemedicine and remote medical consultations, which may allow tourists to receive medical support without the need to be physically present in a particular region. Increased risk in travel may lead to increased attention to security measures and insurance among tourists. Organisers of tours and medical programmes can improve their security systems to attract customers.

In addition, the unstable geopolitical situation may require businesses in the health and medical tourism sector to develop flexible and adaptive programmes, which may include the ability to change or cancel bookings without penalty in case of unforeseen circumstances.

In general, the unstable geopolitical situation can create challenges for the development of health and medical tourism, but also open up new opportunities for creative responses to changes in demand and travel conditions.

After the end of military conflicts in Ukraine, the country has every opportunity to restore its tourism potential by attracting foreign investments, opening new tourist destinations and preserving cultural monuments and cities. Now, interest in Ukraine has increased significantly compared to previous periods, which can contribute to the restoration of the country's tourist attractiveness. Ukrainians themselves, wanting to see their hero cities and communicate with history and culture, can also become a source of support for domestic tourism, which opens up wide opportunities for the development of this sector [3].

After the end of the military conflicts in Ukraine, new opportunities are really opening up for the restoration of the country's tourism potential. Let's see what prospects our country can expect. First of all – attraction of foreign investments. After the end of the conflict, the Ukrainian authorities can work on creating a favorable investment climate to attract foreign investors to the tourism sector. Further, the development of tourism requires the opening of new destinations and attractions, that is, the reconstruction and development of cities, historical sites and nature reserves can become attractive for tourists. The opening of new tourist routes and facilities can lead to increased interest in the country.

After the end of the war and the victory, the interest of tourists in the cultural heritage of our country will increase. Interest in the history and cultural heritage of Ukraine may increase, which in the future may lead to an increase in the tourist flow.

Regarding domestic tourism, the rise of patriotic sentiment after important events can contribute to the growth of tourism, as Ukrainians themselves seek to learn more about their country, visit historical sites and travel around their own country.

However, it is important to consider that the recovery of the tourism sector requires a comprehensive approach, including government measures, marketing strategies, infrastructural improvements and other measures to create a favorable environment for tourism. The success of such recovery also depends on the support of the international community and effective management of resources.

Attracting foreign investment to the tourism sector can contribute to its development and infrastructure improvement. Investors can invest in hotels, restaurants, transport networks and other tourism services, which will improve the quality of service for visitors.

The expansion of tourist infrastructure and the active implementation of marketing strategies can contribute to the opening of new tourist destinations and destinations, which will expand the market and attract the attention of different categories of tourists. Preservation and restoration of historical monuments, museums and other cultural objects can become attractive for tourists who value history and cultural values. A thoughtful marketing campaign will emphasize the uniqueness of the cultural and historical heritage of our territory.

Ukraine can develop partnership relations with other countries and international tourism organizations, which in turn will promote the exchange of experience, technologies and increase the attractiveness of Ukraine for foreign tourists.

The integration of the above perspectives can create a favorable atmosphere for restoring the tourism potential of Ukraine, attracting both foreign tourists and local residents.

The high level of elasticity of demand in the tourist market relative to the growth of the income level can be related to several factors. Human need for recreation, with increasing income, people have more free funds to spend on entertainment and recreation. In this way, the growth of incomes can become an incentive for greater demand for tourist services. As incomes rise, consumers may seek new and more exclusive travel experiences. They can spend more on travel, expand their travel horizons, and choose higher-end hotels and services. As the income level of people in developed countries increases, international tourism may increase. People can travel more abroad for recreation and to discover new cultures. The growth in demand can also stimulate the development of tourism infrastructure such as hotels, restaurants, transportation and other services that meet the growth in demand. The high elasticity of demand can mean that changes in the level of income of consumers have a significant impact on their willingness to spend money on tourism services, which makes this market sensitive to economic changes [2].

The main means of promoting the development of medical and health tourism today is the promotion of a

healthy lifestyle, which is considered an important trend in social development, therefore it is considered logical to create a strategy for the development of regional health and medical tourism destinations for children aimed at improving their health and improving their well-being.

Medical and health tourism for children is considered an important direction, as it contributes to the comprehensive development of younger generations and supports their health and well-being.

Medical and health tourism helps to improve the physical health of children. Staying in the fresh air, movement and interaction with nature contribute to hardening and maintenance of the general physical condition. Such tourist trips contribute to the development of mental health, reduce stress and promote emotional recovery. They can help overcome psychological difficulties and improve the well-being of children. Group trips promote the development of children's social skills. They learn cooperation, communication and interaction with peers, which can positively affect their social development. Medical tourism can include excursions and educational programs that expand children's knowledge of nature, history and culture. This creates unique educational opportunities that are difficult to obtain in other settings. Resting in natural healing places can prevent diseases and improve children's immunity. Medical tourism contributes to the formation of children's respect for nature and the education of environmental awareness. Such tourist trips encourage children to an active lifestyle, developing an interest in physical activities and sports. Medical tourism for children is a relevant and important element of their development, promoting health, personality development and social interaction.

The Odesa region has wonderful natural landscapes and coasts, which create unique opportunities for medical and recreational recreation. Access to medical facilities and clinics that can provide effective medical care for children. A rich history and cultural heritage that can become the basis for the development of educational and cultural programs for children. The city of Odesa and its surrounding areas attract tourists with their atmosphere, sights and entertainment, which can be important for attracting families.

In previous years, the tourism industry was hit hard by the restrictions associated with the COVID-19 pandemic. Gradually, entertainment establishments and tourist facilities resumed their work, but this happened under strict quarantine restrictions. Despite the global difficulties, domestic tourism turned out to be a key factor in the recovery of the industry during 2020-2021. Even with closed borders and the absence of foreign tourists in Ukraine, 2020 was marked by the growth of domestic tourism. Based on the volume of the tourist tax, it can be assumed that tourist flows continue to increase rapidly: in 2021, the increase was 24% compared to 2019. The number of foreigners who crossed the border of Ukraine in 2021 amounted to more than 4 million, which is 26.3% more than in 2020, when quarantine restrictions due to the coronavirus were in effect [4].

The growing importance of tourism and the aggravation of problems related to its development lead to the need to consider changes and search for new directions of development. This causes numerous attempts to adapt the main provisions and principles of the concept of sustainable development to the context of tourism. Sustainable development embodies the idea of achieving harmony between people, society and nature, as well as resolving contradictions between nature and society, ecology and economy, developed and developing countries, as well as taking into account the formed needs of people and reasonable needs. Interrelationship and balance of economic, social, environmental, institutional and innovative-technological components aimed at maximizing human well-being without complicating opportunities for future generations to meet their needs are key aspects [5].

The development of health and medical destinations in Ukraine can be effective if various aspects such as infrastructure, medical services, tourism potential and governance are taken into account [6].

Recommendations for the balanced development of health and wellness destinations:

1. medical services and expertise by ensuring a high standard of medical services and the availability of qualified medical personnel (expanding the range of services, including health, rehabilitation and preventive programmes);
2. providing a comfortable and safe infrastructure for tourists and patients, including hotels, vehicles, parks and other entertainment facilities (development of medical infrastructure, including modern medical facilities and laboratories);
3. active marketing planning to attract the attention of tourists and patients from different regions (use of modern means of communication to promote health destinations);
4. development of the tourism industry - expansion of tourist services, such as excursions, sporting events, cultural events, which complement the medical aspect through cooperation with travel agencies and hotels to create package offers;
5. government regulation through the introduction of strict standards and licences for medical facilities and medical personnel;
6. studying the interests and needs of the local population, i.e. analysing the needs and expectations of the local population to improve accessibility and response to the development of health destinations;
7. establishing partnerships with local authorities, medical institutions and other stakeholders for joint development;
8. involvement of educational institutions and research centres in the process to promote the development of the latest methods and technologies in the field of health tourism and medicine;
9. preservation of natural resources and ecosystems in health destinations, which contributes to the development and support of environmentally friendly technologies and practices in construction and management;

10. introduction of modern technologies to improve the quality of medical services and ensure a comfortable stay of tourists using electronic medical records and other information systems for effective interaction between medical staff and patients;

11. creation and maintenance of sports playgrounds, trails for walking and fitness, as well as organisation of sports events and tournaments that attract the attention of active tourists;

12. involving local people in the planning and implementation of projects to create programmes and activities to support local entrepreneurs and small business development;

13. taking measures to ensure accessibility of medical services and healthcare procedures for various social groups (developing support programmes for those who may need financial or physical assistance);

14. attracting foreign investment for the development of health destinations and medical infrastructure through international agreements and partnerships for the exchange of technological and medical innovations.

These recommendations are intended to ensure the comprehensive development of health and wellness destinations in Ukraine, contributing to high-quality healthcare and improving the tourist attractiveness of the regions.

The overall approach should be integrated and focused on providing quality healthcare services and a pleasant tourist experience [7].

Before starting to develop a strategy for the development of regional medical and health tourism destinations for children, it is necessary to conduct a SWOT analysis to identify potential advantages and

negative factors that may affect the development of medical and health tourism. In this case, the SWOT analysis will help identify possible ways to develop and avoid possible risks for this form of tourism.

SWOT analysis is an important step in the strategic planning of the development of health tourism for children within the regional framework. This analysis allows to systematically identify internal and external factors that may affect the success of the project. At the level of potential benefits, SWOT allows to identify resources that can be maximised to strengthen and promote regional medical tourism. This may include the availability of highly qualified medical personnel, natural healing resources, infrastructure for children and their support. In the context of negative factors, a SWOT helps to identify potential threats and vulnerabilities. For example, possible problems may include insufficient funding, competition from other regions, or the negative impact of changes in legislation. The analysis also provides an opportunity to identify potential ways to develop by leveraging internal strengths and eliminating or reducing the negative impact of external factors. This may include creating marketing campaigns to attract attention, expanding medical services or introducing innovative programmes for children [8, 9].

All of this together contributes to the development of a strategy that takes into account all aspects and maximises the opportunities for the development of health tourism for children in the region.

Let us consider the SWOT analysis of the strategy for the development of health and medical tourism destinations for children in Table 1.

Table 1. SWOT-analysis of the strategy for the development of health-improving tourist destinations for children in the Odesa region

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Natural resources — Healthcare facilities — Cultural resources — Technological innovations — Qualified medical staff 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Insufficiently developed infrastructure — Limitations of accessibility — Low awareness — Seasonality
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Tourism development — Partnerships with organisations — Increasing medical tourism — Possibility of introducing new health programmes — Technological innovations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Competition from other regions — Economic difficulties — Changes in legislation — Military actions — Pandemics and global crises — Climate change

Source: the authors' own elaboration

Natural resources include beautiful natural landscapes and coastlines that can be used for recreational activities. Medical facilities in our regions are of high quality and availability, they can ensure the provision of medical services to children. Cultural resources can include a rich history and cultural heritage, which allows for the development of various educational and cultural programs for children.

Adequate tourism infrastructure and amenities for children and their country are provided to the

underdeveloped infrastructure. As for accessibility constraints – insufficient volume of vehicles and limited access to tourist sites limiting your visitor flow. Low awareness – this refers to a lack of awareness among parents and guardians about existing health and treatment opportunities for children in the region.

The development of tourism refers to the growing interest in health and ecological tourism, which can lead to an increase in the number of tourists. In terms of partnering with organizations, working with

charities and non-profits to support funding and project development can also provide opportunities to attract new potential customers. Under the promotion of medical tourism, we are talking about attracting tourists who are looking for treatment and rehabilitation of children from other regions or countries.

Competition with other regions - this includes other regions that may have more developed programs and infrastructure for children's health. As for economic hardships, so are the possibilities of hardships that may limit financial support and investment in projects. In turn, changes in legislation also have certain threats, they can negatively affect the activities of tourist and medical institutions.

Odesa region has significant potential for the development of medical tourism for children, thanks to its natural resources and access to medical services. However, there is a need to actively work on solutions to weaknesses such as insufficient infrastructure for children and low awareness of the region's opportunities. The search for a financial and effective marketing strategy can contribute to overcoming these problems and the development of health tourism for children in the Odesa region.

SWOT analysis, which is given in the table. 1 allows to identify the key factors that can influence the strategy of development of health and medical tourist destinations for children in the Odesa region. Based on this analysis, effective measures can be developed to maximize the benefits and minimize the negative aspects.

- The key factors that may influence the development strategy of health and medical tourism destinations are
- Medical infrastructure – accessibility and quality of medical facilities: Availability of modern medical facilities with high-quality equipment and qualified medical staff.
- infrastructure for children – playgrounds and entertainment areas. Creation of safe and interesting places for children's recreation and entertainment.

- Natural resources and landscapes – exploitation of natural beauty, maximum use of natural resources and attractive landscapes to create recreational areas.
- tourist potential of the region – cultural and tourist attractions, development of tourist programmes covering cultural and historical attractions that are of interest to children.
- educational and developmental programmes – educational opportunities, development of programmes that combine education and entertainment for children's development.
- partnerships and cooperation – partnerships with hospitals and schools, development of cooperation with medical and educational institutions to expand services.
- Marketing – attracting the attention of parents, developing effective marketing strategies to attract families and raise awareness of existing opportunities.
- Economic factor – financial accessibility for families, developing programmes and packages that are affordable for a wide range of families, taking into account economic opportunities.
- Changes in legislation – compliance with laws and standards, monitoring changes in legislation and standards to ensure compliance and safety.
- Technological innovation – using technology for learning and entertainment, adopting the latest technology to improve the quality of services and learning.

These factors are of great importance when formulating a strategy for the development of health and wellness tourism destinations for children, and their interaction can determine the success and popularity of such destinations in the region.

The task of maximising the advantages and minimising the negative aspects identified in the SWOT analysis may include a number of specific measures. Let's look at the proposals for the development of health and medical tourist destinations for children in Odesa region in Table 2.

Table 2. Proposals for the development of health and wellness tourist destinations

Maximising benefits	Minimising negative factors	Maximising benefits	Minimising negative factors
Development of treatment programmes		Development of infrastructure for children	
Creation of unique entertainment zones		Raising awareness of opportunities	
Cultural and tourist activities		Partnerships with hospitals and schools	
Organisation of sports tournaments		Financial transparency	
Development of educational programmes		Active feedback policy	
		Adaptation to legislation	

Source: the authors' own elaboration

These measures can help to preserve and enhance the advantages identified in the SWOT analysis and reduce the impact of negative aspects on the strategy for the development of health and medical tourist destinations for children in the Odesa region.

The creation of a strategy for the development of health and wellness tourist destinations for children in the Odesa region can help not only attract more

tourists, but also contribute to the health and development of children.

To further create the strategy, a survey was launched among reviewers on the topic of people's interest in health facilities for children. A total of 100 people took part in the survey. The questionnaire consisted of 12 questions and was distributed to people living in the Odesa region.

According to the survey, the respondents have the following structure: 67% women and 33% men. Age category of respondents: 59% - 30 to 50 years old, 36% - 18 to 30 years old, 5% - 50 years old and older.

The survey of this sample yielded the following results:

- Regarding the frequency of searching for wellness centres, the majority (51.1%) of respondents answered that they rarely search for such centres, 25% said they never searched for such centres and 23.9% said they often search for wellness centres. The majority of respondents indicated that the presence of such factors as a safe environment for children (48.9%), physical activity (44.6%), and opportunities for children to spend time outdoors (43.5%) are important to them, and (40.2%) of respondents voted for all the options presented.
- The majority (83%) of respondents indicated in their answers that they would be interested in additional services for children, such as music lessons, master classes, etc. 9.8% said that they did not care whether there would be such services and 6.5% of reviewers said that they were not interested in additional services.
- The majority (43.5%) of reviewers said that they could be encouraged to choose a contour health centre by all the answers provided. 41.3% noted that the reputation of the centre is important to them.
- Almost all (91.3%) of the reviewers said that the availability of special facilities for children with special needs is indeed important. 4.3% said they had a child with special needs. The rest (4.4%) said that such conditions were not necessary.
- The majority (43.3%) said that they are limited by the location of such centres, and some (41.1%) said that they have financial constraints. Others (35.6%) said that they are affected by their work schedule and the opening hours of the centre.
- A large number (53.3%) of respondents said that they would like to receive information through social media. Some (25%) said they did not want spam and others (21.7%) said they would like to receive information about health centres by email.
- 36.5% of respondents said they expect a 14-day or more recovery period. 29.4% said they were

satisfied with a 10-day period. 28.1 per cent said they would like to spend 7 days on rehabilitation. 7.1% said that 5 days of rehabilitation would be enough.

- As for the pricing policy, the conclusions are as follows: 33.7% said that the price from 1000 to 1500 UAH (for 1 day) would be affordable for more families; 31.5% said that the amount of 500-1000 UAH is affordable; 19.6% said that the price in the range of 200-500 UAH is more affordable.

Based on the analysis of this survey, we can say that people are really interested in health centres for children. Respondents noted that safety for children, the availability of special facilities for children with special needs and the location of such centres are important. As for receiving information, many said they would like to see it on their social media. The period of rehabilitation and price - in general, it can be determined that the majority of respondents estimate the optimal period of rehabilitation at 10-14 days and are ready to spend from UAH 500 to 1500 per day, while noting that a lower pricing policy in the range of UAH 200-500 is also convenient for some respondents.

Conclusions

The study of the development of regional health and wellness tourist destinations for children revealed important aspects that determine the success and sustainability of such projects. The prospects for the development of health and medical tourism in an unstable geopolitical situation were noted, as an unstable geopolitical situation can affect tourist flows and require flexibility and strategic planning from industry participants.

The analysis of the need for regional health and wellness tourist destinations for children in the Odesa region indicates a significant demand for such types of recreation among younger groups of the population. Children need access to quality medical care and health treatments that can be provided in specialised institutions and resorts. In addition, it has been found that the development of infrastructure for children's health tourism has great potential for regional tourism development and improving the health and well-being of the younger generation. Further research can help improve programmes and services to meet the health tourism needs of children in the Odesa region.

Abstract

This article is devoted to the analysis of the need for regional health-improving tourist destinations for children on the example of Odesa region. This topic highlights the importance of this tourism segment and its prospects in the context of the unstable geopolitical situation during the war in Ukraine.

Particular attention is paid to recommendations for the balanced development of health resorts, taking into account the current challenges and opportunities in a crisis situation. The effective development of health and wellness destinations in Ukraine requires the integrated inclusion of various aspects, including infrastructure, medical services, tourism potential and governance. Infrastructure development, such as ensuring accessibility to medical facilities, rehabilitation centres and sports facilities, is key to providing quality conditions for recreation and treatment. Improved healthcare services, including the development of the latest technologies and qualified medical personnel, help to increase the attractiveness of destinations for younger tourists. The tourism potential also plays an important role in the development of health and wellness destinations, as the attractiveness of local attractions, cultural events and other tourist attractions attracts holidaymakers.

The article applies SWOT-analysis, which allowed identifying strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in the strategy of development of health tourism for children in the Odesa region.

The article conducts a survey, which was carried out through a questionnaire. The survey involved 100 respondents from the Odesa region. The analysis has shown a significant demand for regional health and medical tourism destinations for children in the Odesa region, especially among the younger population groups. Children today need high-quality medical care and health procedures that can be provided in specialised institutions and resorts.

Future research can contribute to improving programmes and services to meet the health tourism needs of children in the Odesa region and serve as a basis for further strategies for the development of tourism and health improvement for children in the region, contributing to its attractiveness and competitiveness.

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Посилання на статтю:

Dobrianska N.A. Analysis of the Need for Regional Health and Treatment Tourist Destinations for Children / N.A. Dobrianska, S.S. Chernousova, L.R. Salenko // Економіка: реалії часу. Науковий журнал. – 2024. – № 1 (71). – С. 87-95. – Режим доступу: <https://economics.net.ua/files/archive/2024/No1/87.pdf>. DOI: 10.15276/ETR.01.2024.11. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10982674.

Reference a Journal Article:

Dobrianska N.A. Analysis of the Need for Regional Health and Treatment Tourist Destinations for Children / N.A. Dobrianska, S.S. Chernousova, L.R. Salenko // Economics: time realities. Scientific journal. – 2024. – № 1 (71). – P. 87-95. – Retrieved from: <https://economics.net.ua/files/archive/2024/No1/87.pdf>. DOI: 10.15276/ETR.01.2024.11. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10982674.

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